

Water Quality Features' Changes

WQeMS platform, showing the satellite-derived Secchi Disk Depth indicator for Polyphytos lake, Greece, based on Sentinel-2 imagery

Aim of the service line

Observe the **changes of water quality parameters** of a water body in an **operational** manner, covering **slow-** and **fast-developing phenomena**, using **satellite data** and employing validated **processing chains**.

Underwater dam leading to increased Chlorophyll values in pre-reservoir of Saldenbach reservoir, Germany, derived from Sentinel-2

Bloom Events Detection

WQeMS platform, showing the satellite-derived Harmful Algal Bloom indicator for Eibenstock reservoir, Germany, based on Sentinel-2 imagery. For the selected data, no algal bloom is detected, also visible in the histogram view in the top left corner.

Aim of the service line

Detect and observe the **development of potentially harmful algal blooms** on a water body at different spatial scales, using **satellite data** and employing validated **processing chains**.

Harmful Algal Bloom indicator, derived from Sentinel-2 imagery (left) and WorldView-3 imagery (right), showing the importance of covering different spatial scales in the observation of algal blooms

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Water quality monitoring with satellites and automated in situ observations in Finland

As part of the WQeMS portfolio Syke's TARKKA service provides free and open access to satellite and other observations from Finland and the Baltic Sea

EO, GIS and in situ materials that can be visualized in the map view

Map view showing turbidity values (from Sentinel-2) in different parts of the lake over a true color image

Chl-a time series plot showing satellite estimates (S2) together with in situ observations from the location of an automated measurement station.

Tracking the open surface water dynamics through time

An abrupt **increase** in the water extent of reservoirs not only affects the concentration of the solid material and of the substances in water, but also acts as entry path of potential pollutants.

On the other hand, a significant **decrease** in the water extent may have an impact on the concentration of the dissolved matter and the inflow or speed of water.

Land Water Transition Zone Change Detection service has been devised to **monitor water extent fluctuations** of open surface water reservoirs.

It exploits **Earth Observation data** from the Copernicus mission to capture changes in land/ water cover in open surface water reservoirs.

Monitoring through proven workflows assimilating EO data

Assessments exploit both multispectral (e.g., Sentinel-2) and microwave data (e.g., Sentinel - 1) to achieve a high frequency registration of the situation on the ground.

This may take place as a seasonal (see figure on the right) or a two instance change detection analysis (see example in the figure below).

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- ✓ Proven and adapted workflows at multiple sites across Europe reaching up to 98% accuracies (applied at various scenery types)
- ✓ Enhanced frequency of information retrieval with proven credible results
- ✓ Fully unsupervised performance

Extreme events detection (Floods / Oil spills)

Water We Drink...

WQeMS is a water quality monitoring service for water utilities based on the free Copernicus satellite data, providing an extreme events detection service using advanced AI techniques to identify and monitor extreme events, that degrade inland water quality.

Floods Service

The flood service uses Sentinel-1 data to extract information from time series patterns with a Deep Learning model, and maps flood events in drinking water reservoirs with high temporal and spatial resolution, providing valuable information for end-users, especially water utilities.

Pixels predicted as ongoing extreme flood (yellow) in Giaretta lake

Monitoring Services:

- Flood Events
- Muddy Waters
- Hydrocarbon Formations

What we do

- Use satellite data
- Monitor areas across EU countries
- Apply AI techniques to monitor extreme events
- Offer useful statistics

Muddy Water Service

The muddy water service uses Sentinel-2 data to monitor sediment-laden water in drinking water reservoirs. An ensemble machine learning model generates a presence and probability map for muddy water and provides valuable information for emergency management.

Probability (left) and binary (right) map for muddy waters in Polyphytos lake

Extreme events detection (Floods / Oil spills)

Hydrocarbon Formations Service

The oil spill service uses Sentinel-2 satellite data and a Deep Neural Network model to identify potential hydrocarbon formations in inland waters, providing end-users with useful information to take timely mitigation actions.

Potential hydrocarbon presence in Polyphytos lake (red); Google Earth used as basemap.

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Benefits

- Available for water utilities and end-users
- Monitor reservoirs with high spatial resolution and frequency
- Authorities can identify potential issues earlier
- Minimize impact of pollution with less human resources

Gain for the water utilities

- Users will be able to monitor drinking water reservoirs with high spatial resolution and at regions where there is no direct access.
- Costs related to in-situ sensors and excess human labor can be decreased.

Gain for the authorities and citizens

- Authorities which benefit from the drinking water production, will be able to get insight of the current status of a given area of interest in order to identify potential persistent issues and tackle them accordingly.
- Citizens will have access to water of higher quality.

WQeMS e-Training Platform towards capacity building and sustainability

The innovation process is linked to the ability of the professionals to accept and adopt state-of-the-art technological tools and workflows in their daily practice.

In WQeMS, we put emphasis to the adoption and sustainability of the developed services, aiming for the water professionals to acquire the necessary capacity (skills and competencies) for the use of the remote sensing and monitoring results.

Capacity building for inland water sources earth observation

UNIT 1.1 - INTRODUCTION TO COPERNICUS

Copernicus Programme

- A European Union's Earth observation programme, coordinated and managed by the European Commission, European Space Agency (ESA), EU member States and EU Agencies.
- Considered as a part of a public service framework, allowing full, free and open access to all data collected.

Why AI is so important for earth observation?

- Fast and specialized hardware and computing (GPUs)
- Access to more and more data, "on-demand" data
- Use the potential to anticipate and address the biggest challenges
- Help to simplify administrative tasks (AI)
- Advance the accuracy of assessing incidents

Drag the words into the correct boxes

Land Applications: **Water Safety**, **Desertification**, **Coastal Zone**, **Land Cover, Use and Change Detection Mapping**, **Bio-geophysical Variable Monitoring**, **Risk Mapping**, **Precision Farming**, **Forest Monitoring**

Maritime Applications: **Marine & Coastal Environment**, **Coasts & Seasonal Forecasting**, **Sea Ice**, **Marine Safety**, **Marine Resources**

Interactive training content and assessment

Benefits to water consumers

The sustainable use of the technologies will facilitate the long-term benefit to the water consumers, who will enjoy the basic right for high-quality water.

e-Training Service

- ✓ A set of 4 training modules
- ✓ Engaging training material
- ✓ Interactive assessment units

[https:// training.wqems.eu](https://training.wqems.eu)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action programme under Grant Agreement No 101004157

Interactive training content and flexible management

LEARNING PATH COURSES

TRAINING CATALOGUE

Flexible training content management

Training Modules and Pathways

1. Understanding Copernicus Data and Services.
2. Technical aspects in earth observation services.
3. Inland water features' estimation service, enabled by earth observation.
4. Use-cases and applications

Different training pathways have been defined to address the diverse needs for skillsets by different types of stakeholders.

Build on top of Open Source Tools

The e-Training Service is built on the Opigno LMS (<https://www.opigno.org/>), an open source Drupal-9 enabled tool, distributed under the terms of the GNU GPL v.3 license.

Access to the training content is provided free of charge.

Adoption statistics to facilitate decision making

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EMPOWER WATER UTILITIES IMPROVING WATER QUALITY MONITORING

Exploiting Sentinel data to provide **quality monitoring** of open surface water reservoirs valorized for the delivery of drinking water at a fine spatial resolution.

Complete set of tools to support water utilities:

- ▶ Automated generation of **geospatial maps, statistics** and **detailed information** on slow and fast developing phenomena,
- ▶ **Alerting** in case water-related issues are detected through social media or analysing monitored parameters.

WQeMS Platform components and tools

Interfaces for the visualization of geospatial maps

CONTINUOUS

Continuously monitors water reservoirs, generates geospatial maps each day and detects water related-issues.

- ▶ Recommended for **routinely operational monitoring** and **early-warning**.

ON-DEMAND

Generates one-off geospatial maps of a given area at a Given time.

- ▶ Recommended for **emergency management** or for any type of issues spotted in an water reservoir.

INTEGRATE, EXTEND, CUSTOMIZE

Developers interfaces (APIs, OGC Web Services)

WQeMS can **interface existing Earth Observation systems**, such as the **Copernicus Services** and the **Group of Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS)** platform.

A federated approach enable to include additional data providers and to connect to future third-party commercial or non-commercial services.

A microservices architectural approach ensure **scalability, flexibility** and **evolvability**.

A set of features allow water experts, developers, and researchers to **integrate WQeMS functionalities into existing Decision Support Systems** as well as to improve current methods and test alternative solutions.

The platform provides **APIs and Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Web Services** to access data using popular, well-established standards, to automatically disseminate up-to-date geospatial maps and related statistics.

WQeMS Federated solution

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Introduction

WQeMS explores the utilization of social media to obtain crowdsourced data that are relevant to water quality and enhance awareness using a novel source of information.

Service description

WQeMS provides 5 services to crowdsourced information about water-related incidents:

- The Social Media Crawler for real-time collection of relevant tweets.
- The Crowdsourcing Mobile App where Android users can report water issues.
- A parser that that ingests daily new citizen algae bloom observations from SYKE'S CitObs API.
- An Alerting Module that generates warnings based on certain thresholds on the above social data.
- A Crowdsourcing Dashboard that visualizes the warnings.

Alerting Module Framework

Service results

The Alerting Module constantly collects:

- Tweets about water quality & pollution, oil spills, algae bloom, turbidity, etc.
- Citizens complaints through a mobile APP.
- Citizen observations for algae bloom for the region of Finland.

Dynamically create alerts and provide a Crowdsourcing Dashboard with a user-friendly interface for and filtering crowdsourced alerts on a map

Alerting module (Reporting & Crowdsourcing)

Gain for the user

Providing water utility operators with crowdsourced alerts of potential water issues.

- Saving human resources.
- Offering better coverage.

Crowdsourcing Mobile App

Key points

- Analyse crowdsource water related information in real time.
- Monitor water issues.
- Raise awareness about water-related events.
- Enable quick detection and response to emerging water-related incidents.

Crowdsourcing Dashboard

Gain for the end user

Enables a more efficient and streamlined way for citizens to post water-related complaints through their smartphones.

- Avoiding lengthy phone calls.
- Improving the customer services quality and the customer satisfaction.

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